

DEVELOPMENT OF A DESIGN RESEARCH ALGORITHM FOR SERVICE PERSONAL ROBOTS BASED ON THE USE OF TYPIIFICATION METHOD

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Abstract

Design research is a pre-project investigation necessary to create a new product. It is quite challenging to consider design research separately from design thinking, which is one of the leading tools for conducting such research. Design thinking is closely linked to project awareness. According to one of the founders of design thinking philosophy - design is essentially an artificial process that can be controlled to create something more perfect compared to natural processes that require human intervention. Natural processes arise out of necessity, while artificial ones provide opportunities and are responsive to the environment.

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That is, engineering, architecture, painting, and others are not necessary but possible processes under certain circumstances, which means they involve design. Design thinking creates a product oriented towards people, users. Therefore, to design something new, it is necessary to conduct research that focuses on user needs, and only then consider technical and economic possibilities. To streamline the process of designing a new product, it is necessary to define its stages and formalize them. Research allows for more effective collaboration with the client and immerses the designer in the context of the task at hand. Any research

begins with the formation of initial information on specific indicators. Primary research is necessary to understand who and what to design for. Then, the collected information must be processed appropriately through data summarization and grouping. Secondary research is used as a means of further shaping the design and sales strategy: what should be prioritized to attract users. American industrial designer, philosopher, and design theorist method of implementing design for its intended purpose, i.e., the method of developing design activities, highlights specific primary functional criteria for evaluating the product. His approach is cyclical, with all elements interconnected (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Method of developing design activities from the perspective of design theory

He places the method that defines the interaction of tools, processes, and technologies at the core of product development. Before and during the design process, one should ask how functionally the designed product will be used, what qualities it should possess depending on its functional purpose as a tool, means of communication, or symbol. The end product should satisfy human needs, not just momentarily but genuinely. Among these requirements, also highlights telethesis, as the characteristic(s) of the product that should reflect the time and conditions, correspond to the place where the product will operate. Telethesis is closely linked to associations that determine adherence to certain values that are prominent markers of the target audience.

Not the least, although quite contradictory, role, in his opinion, is played by aesthetics, for which there is

no specific measure but which serves as a measure of the quality of the design research process. The classical sociological approach to research is linear: the question posed at the beginning of the research determines the structure and methods of the research (Figure 2). American sociologist David Morgan suggests revising the classical theoretical approach by considering design research as a practical cyclical process in which the selected research data determine the research questions. The researcher must understand the set and boundaries of their competencies and be able to identify the potential of both existing data and possible developments (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Approaches to design research from a sociological perspective

Depending on the research strategy, two approaches are distinguished for their implementation: qualitative and quantitative. Usually, qualitative and quantitative strategies are implemented simultaneously. The most productive approach to obtaining research results is the "sequential contributions" principle, which allows for a chain of continuity between data: the results of one method serve as data for moving on to the next method. Marketing views design as a business activity that starts with defining corporate objectives. During the implementation of the design strategy, tasks receive material solutions that are released to the market to generate income. To create a competitive product, it is necessary to have information about the design requirements. To achieve this, market research should be conducted. Among many business leaders, there is a viewpoint that the main goal of marketing is to stimulate maximum consumption, which, in turn, stimulates production growth. This idea is based on the

belief that the more people consume, the happier they become. However, not all marketers agree with this statement. Some, for example, believe that the goal of marketing is not to achieve the maximum level of consumption but to maximize consumer satisfaction. Unfortunately, measuring satisfaction is quite complex. The developers who determine the product or service strategy often lack information about what happens to these products or services after they reach consumers directly. Therefore, he proposes a special approach to developing new products – impression-based design. In his opinion, products developed by designers occupy an intermediate position between the business world and the world of consumers. Therefore, it is necessary to merge these two worlds by formulating design tasks in such a way as to consider, firstly, the conditions of product use and, secondly, consumer impressions (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Approaches to design research from a marketing perspective

To understand what impression consumers get from using service personal robotics, it is necessary to consider, firstly, the characteristics of the objects and, secondly, the impressions obtained from them.

The following characteristics should be distinguished for objects of industrial design: functionality (expands or improves user capabilities); informativeness (provides users with knowledge); communicativeness (facilitates or enhances the communication process); aesthetics (evokes emotions from the perception of beauty); status (indicates membership in a social group); and sensuality (stimulates user emotions and those of their surroundings). Activity development method, where criteria such as tools, materials, and technologies correspond to functionality; use as a means of communication is communicativeness; telethesis, based on knowledge about society and nature, their characteristics, represents in formativeness; aesthetics remains in its place in both approaches, serving as the content of ideal object perception by humans; the need that determines not only survival but also an individual's identity in society is realized through status; and associations, inseparably linked with family, environment, education, and culture of a specific individual, are identical to sensuality.

The typology of characteristics of industrial design objects allows for describing service personal robots based on specific characteristics:

1. **Functionality**: Service personal robots assist with household chores, provide security and supervision, can carry loads, and help the elderly and disabled individuals. They also entertain and contribute to leisure activities. The design and planning of these robots should be based on a method that, considering their

range of functions, allows for the selection of materials and technologies for their production.

2. **Informativeness**: A service personal robot is an information-rich product that not only receives information but is also capable of transmitting it personally or remotely. The robot's external appearance should be designed taking into account knowledge about its surrounding environment and its interaction with humans, i.e., it should be ergonomic and harmonious.

3. **Communicativeness**: A service personal robot, as a social object, is part of social life, creating new forms of communication and developing communication possibilities. These forms of communication are expressed semiotically in the search for new forms of the robot's external appearance.

4. **Aesthetics**: Technology is the result of the process of aestheticizing material culture, and a robot, as the pinnacle of its creation, can attract or repel, but it rarely leaves anyone indifferent. The artistic image should possess both constructive and semiotic qualities, becoming the necessary final criterion for stylistic characterization.

Status: The subculture of users of high-tech items is expressed in the clear differentiation of certain distinctions and belonging to different social groups through the demonstration of ownership. This characteristic is realized in the robot's external appearance through the use of modern, high-tech, expensive materials and their special processing.

The approaches to design research and the typology of characteristics of industrial design objects described above allow for the development of a methodology for design research of service personal robotics (Figure 4), which is, on one hand, a linear process based

on primary data, the analysis of which helps formulate questions and select research methods. On the other

hand, it is a cyclical process where each element complements the others.

****Figure 4 - Methodology for Design Research of Service Personal Robots****

Typifying existing service personal robot objects based on characteristics identified by manufacturers and consumers reveals the possibility of posing the question to the designer of how to design such a product. It allows for the formation of a group of factors influencing the formative process. Subsequent data processing using statistical analysis methods makes it possible to create a classifier of formative characteristics for practical use in the design of service personal robotics.

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